

**A STUDY OF MIGRAINE IN DIFFERENT AGE GROUPS OF RURAL AND URBAN
POPULATION OF ELURU, ELURU DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH”**

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ABSTRACT

Migraine is a genetically influenced complex disorder characterized by episodes of moderate-to-severe headache, most often unilateral and generally associated with nausea and increased sensitivity to light and sound. Migraine is a common cause of disability and loss of work. Migraine attacks are complex brain events that unfold over hours to days in a recurrent matter. The most common type of migraine is without aura (75% of cases). Migraines occur in both children and adults but affect adult women three times more often than men. Migraines are genetic. Most migraine sufferers have a family history of the disorder. They also frequently occur in people who have other medical conditions. Depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, sleep disorders, and epilepsy are more common in individuals with migraine than in the general population. Individuals who have pre - migraine symptoms referred to as aura have a slightly increased risk of having a stroke. Migraine in women often relates to changes in hormones. They may begin at the start of the first menstrual cycle or during pregnancy. Most women see improvement after menopause, although surgical removal of the ovaries usually worsens migraines. Women with migraine who take oral contraceptives may experience changes in the frequency and severity of attacks, while women who do not suffer from headaches may develop migraines as a side effect of oral contraceptives. Required data was collected from 210 subjects in selected areas of Eluru, Eluru District of Andhra Pradesh” by Survey method using a standard questionnaire.

KEYWORDS: Migraine, Problems in women and men, causes.

INTRODUCTION

Migraine is a genetically influenced complex disorder characterized by episodes of moderate-to-severe headache, most often unilateral and generally associated with nausea and increased sensitivity to light and sound. The word migraine is derived from the Greek word "Hemikrania," later converted into Latin as "hemigranea." The French translation of such a term is "migraine." Migraine is a common cause of disability and loss of work. Migraine attacks are complex brain events that unfold over hours to days in a recurrent manner. The most common type of migraine is without aura (75% of cases). Migraines occur in both children and adults but affect adult women three times more often than men. Migraines are genetic. Most migraine sufferers have a family history of the disorder.^[1] They also frequently occur in people who have other medical conditions. Depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, sleep disorders, and epilepsy are more common in individuals with migraine than in the general population. Individuals who have pre-migraine symptoms referred to as aura have a slightly increased risk of having a stroke.

Migraine in women often relates to changes in hormones. The headaches may begin at the start of the first menstrual cycle or during pregnancy. Most women see improvement after menopause, although surgical removal of the ovaries usually worsens migraines. Women with migraine who take oral contraceptives may experience changes in the frequency and severity of attacks, while women who do not suffer from headaches may develop migraines as a side effect of oral contraceptives.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a cross-sectional survey design to collect data from residents of selected areas in Eluru, Eluru District, Andhra Pradesh. A total of 21 areas within Eluru were systematically selected for the study and data was collected from 210 subjects through structured interviews conducted using a standard questionnaire.

- Pratikolla Lanka
- Annapaneni Vari Gudem
- Vanguru
- Thimmarao Gudem
- Gajulagondi
- Nandigama Lanka near CSI Church
- Nandigama Lanka near Community Hall
- Jaggavaram
- Palakunta
- Ameenapeta Eluru
- Sivalayam Temple Lane
- Eastern Street, Eluru
- Kaikaluru
- Bose Bomma Center
- Chipurugudem
- Saibaba Temple Lane
- Vidhyanagar
- Sriramnagar
- Velagapadu
- Pulla
- Pathepeta Vempadu
- Kotha Petavempadu

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Characteristics of the study population.

Age Group	Males	Females	Total
15-20	8(3.809)	29(13.809)	37(17.619)
21-30	13(6.190)	49(23.333)	62(29.523)
31-35	7(3.333)	18(8.571)	25(11.904)
36-40	8(3.809)	16(7.614)	24(11.428)
41-45	6(2.857)	22(10.476)	28(13.333)
46-55	6(2.857)	13(6.190)	19(9.047)
56-60	4(1.904)	11(5.238)	15(7.142)

- Table:1 Shows the total no of male and females according to their age group in the Eluru district
- In the age group of 15-20, 3.809%, are males and 13.809% are females and the total count was 17.619%.
- In the age group of 21-30, 6.190% are males and 23.333% are females and the total count was 29.523%.
- In the age group of 31-35, 3.333% are males, 8.571% are females and the total count was 11.904%.
- In the age group of 36-40, 3.809% are males, 7.614% are females and the total count was 11.428%.
- In the age group of 41-45, 2.857% are males, 10.476% are females and the total count was 13.333%.
- In the age group of 46-55, 2.857% are males, 6.190% are females and the total count was 9.047%. In the age group of 56-60, 1.904% are males, of 5.238% are females and the total count was 7.142%.
- In the age group of 56-60, 1.904% are males, 5.238% are females and the total count was 7.142 %

Table 2: Occupation and family history of Migraine by Age group.

Age Group	Occupation	Family History	
15-20	Students -29(13.809), Daily labors -8(3.809)	Yes -9(9.285)	No-28(13.333)
21-30	Housewives-25(11.904), Students-20(9.423), Job's-9(4.285), Daily labors -8(3.809)	Yes -22(10.476)	No-40(19.04)
31-35	Daily labours-12(5.714), Student -1(0.476), Housewives-10(4.76), Job's-2(0.952)	Yes -19(9.047)	No-6(2.857)
36-40	Daily labours-10(4.761), Housewives-7(3.333), Job's-7(3.333)	Yes - 13 (6.190)	No-11(5.238)
41-45	Daily labours-13(6.190), Housewives-11(5.230), Job's-4(1.904)	Yes -13 (6.190)	No-15(7.142)
46-55	Daily labours-6(2.857), Housewives-8(3.809), Job's -5(2.380)	Yes - 8(3.809)	No-11(5.238)
56-60	Daily labours-3(1.428), Housewives-10(4.761), Job's -2(0.952)	Yes - 4 (1.904)	No-11(5.238)

- Table:2 shows the occupation and family history of the subjects
- Most of them are students, housewives, daily labors, etc.
- The family history mentions whether it is by genetics or by normal (lifestyle/physical activity).
- In the age group of 15-20, students are 13.809%, daily labors are 3.809%, and family history was 9.285%.
- In the age group of 21-30, students are 9.423%, housewives are 11.904%, job holders are 4.285%, and daily labors are 3.809%.
- In the age group of 31-35, students are 0.476%, housewives are 4.76%, job holders are 0.952%, daily labors are 5.714%.
- In the age group of 36-40, housewives are 3.333%, job holders are 3.333%, daily labors are 4.761%.
- In the age group of 41-45, housewives are 5.230%, job holders are 1.904%, daily labors are 6.190%.

- In the age group of 46-55, housewives are 3.809%, job holders are 2.380%, daily labors are 2.857%.
- In the age group of 56-60, housewives are 4.761%, job holders are 0.952%, daily labors are 1.428%.

Table 3: General Health Conditions associated with migraine by age group.

Age Group	General Health condition	Migraine Frequency (No./%)	Food cravings or lack of appetite	Feeling Thirst	Mood changes	Feeling tired	Weakness
15-20	Normal (17.619)	Mild-23(10.95) High-14(6.666)	Food cravings-24(11.428) Lack of appetite -13(6.19)	Yes-21(10) No-16(7.169)	Yes-29(13.809) No-8(3.809)	Yes-27(12.857) No-10(4.761)	Yes-27(12.857) No-10(4.761)
21-30	Normal (29.523)	Mild-37(17.619) High-25(11.904)	Food cravings-38(18.09) Lack of appetite-24(11.428)	Yes-33(15.714) No-29(13.809)	Yes-43(20.476) No-19(9.047)	Yes-42(20) No-20(9.523)	Yes-47(22.380) No-15(7.142)
31-35	Normal (11.904)	Mild-13(6.190) High-12(5.714)	Food cravings -11(5.238) Lack of appetite-14(8.571)	Yes-20(9.523) No-5(2.380)	Yes-17(8.095) No-8(3.809)	Yes-22(10.476) No-3(1.428)	Yes-18(8.571) No-7(3.333)
36-40	Normal (11.428)	Mild-10(4.761) High-14(6.666)	Food cravings-11(5.238) Lack of appetite-13(6.190)	Yes -18(8.571) No-6(2.857)	Yes-20(9.523) No-4(1.904)	Yes-21(10) No-3(1.428)	Yes-20(9.523) No-4(1.904)
41-45	Normal (13.333)	Mild-18(8.571) High-10(4.761)	Food cravings-17(8.095) Lack of appetite-11(5.238)	Yes-11(5.238) No-17(8.095)	Yes-13(6.490) No-15(7.142)	Yes-17(8.095) No-11(5.238)	Yes-18(8.571) No-10(4.761)
46-55	Normal (9.047)	Mild-15(7.142) High -4(1.904)	Food cravings-11(5.238) Lack of appetite-8(3.809)	Yes-12(5.714) No-7(3.333)	Yes-11(5.238) No-8(3.809)	Yes-11(5.238) No-8(3.809)	Yes-13(6.190) No-6(2.857)
56-60	Normal (7.142)	Mild-12(5.174) High -3(1.428)	Food cravings-11(5.238) Lack of appetite-4(1.904)	Yes-11(5.238) No-4(1.904)	Yes-8(3.809) No-7(3.333)	Yes-10(4.761) No-5(2.380)	Yes-8(3.809) No-7(3.333)

- Table: 3 shows the general condition of the subjects, their migraine frequency, their food cravings, lack of appetite, thirstiness, mood changes, tiredness and weaknesses.
- Health conditions were normal and migraine frequencies are between mild to high ranges.
- The age group of 15-20 shows migraine frequency-mild in 10.95%, high- 6.666%,11.428% food cravings and 6.19% lack of appetite,10% thirstiness, mood changes in13.809%, tiredness in 12.857% and weakness in 12.857%.
- The age group of 21-30 shows migraine frequency -mild-17.619%, high-11.904%, food cravings and lack of appetite in 18.09% and 11.428%, thirstiness in15.71%, mood changes in 20.476%, tiredness in 20%, and weaknesses in 22.380%
- The age group of 31-35 shows migraine frequency -mild- 6.190%, high-5.714%, food cravings and lack of appetite in 5.238% and 8.571%, thirstiness in 9.523%, mood changes in 8.095%, tiredness in10.476%, and weaknesses in 8.571%
- The age group of 36-40shows migraine frequency -mild- 4.761%, high-6.666% food cravings and lack of appetite in 5.238% and 6.190%, thirstiness in 8.571%, mood changes in 9.523%, tiredness in10%, and weaknesses in 9.523%
- The age group of 41-45 shows migraine frequency -mild 8.571%, high4.761% food cravings and lack of appetite in 5.238% and 6.190%, thirstiness in 5.238%, mood changes in 6.490%, tiredness in 8.095%, and weaknesses in 8.571%
- The age group of 46-55 shows migraine frequency mild- 7.142%, high-1.904% food cravings and lack of appetite in 5.238% and 3.809%, thirstiness in 5.714%, mood changes in 5.238%, tiredness in 5.238%, and weaknesses in 6.190%.
- The age group of 56-60 shows migraine frequency -mild - 5.174%, high-1.428% food cravings and lack of appetite in 5.238% and 1.904%, thirstiness in 5.238%, mood changes in 3.809%, tiredness in 4.761%, and weaknesses in 3.809%

Table 4: Symptoms of Migraine by Age group.

Age Group	Obesity	Sensitive to light	Sensitive to sound	Sensitive to smell	Fatigue	Constipation or diarrhea	Not be able to see at all	Have tingling or numbness	Not be able to speak	Notice changes in smell,
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								on one side of your body	clearly	taste, or touch
15-20	Yes-9 (4.285) No-28 (13.33)	Yes-23 (10.95) No-14 (6.666)	Yes-21 (10) No-16 (7.619)	Yes-19 (9.047) No-18 (8.571)	Yes-21 (10) No-16 (7.67)	C. Yes- 8(3.809) No-20(9.523) D. Yes- 9 (4.285)	Yes-16(7.6) No-21 (10)	Yes-16(7.16) No-21(10)	Yes-13(6.19) No-24(11.42)	Yes-14(6.66) No-23(10.95)
21-30	Yes-22 (10.476) No-40 (19.047)	Yes-36 (17.14) No-26 (12.38)	Yes-40 (19.04) No-22 (10.476)	Yes-28 (13.33) No-34 (16.19)	Yes-24 (11.4) No-38 (18.09)	C. Yes-18 (8.571) No-31(14.76) D. Yes-13(6.190)	Yes-28(13.3) No-34 (16.19)	Yes-42(20) No-20(9.52)	Yes-28(13.33) No-34(16.19)	Yes-28(13.33) No-34(16.19)
31-35	Yes-20 (9.523) No-5 (2.380)	Yes-18 (8.571) No-7 (3.333)	Yes-16 (5.619) No-9 (4.285)	Yes-18 (8.09) No-8 (3.809)	Yes-19 (9.047) No-6 (2.857)	C. Yes-14 (6.66) No-5(2.380) D. Yes-6 (2.857)	Yes-21(10) No-4(1.90)	Yes-21(10) No-4(1.90)	Yes-9(4.28) No-16(7.61)	Yes-11(5.23) No-14(6.66)
36-40	Yes-12 (5.714) No-12 (5.714)	Yes-10 (4.761) No-14 (6.666)	Yes-17 (8.09) No-7 (3.333)	Yes-13 (6.190) No-11 (5.238)	Yes-8 (3.809) No-16 (7.619)	C. Yes-6(2.857) No -6(2.857) D. Yes-12 (5.714)	Yes-17(8.09) No-7 (3.333)	Yes-18(8.57) No-6 (2.857)	Yes-8(3.80) No-16(7.61)	Yes-9(4.28) No-15(7.14)
41-45	Yes-10 (4.761) No-18 (+8.571)	Yes-15 (7.142) No-13 (6.190)	Yes-14 (6.666) No-14 (6.666)	Yes-16 (7.619) No-12 (5.714)	Yes-13 (6.190) No-15 (7.142)	C. Yes-9(4.285) No -10(4.761) D. Yes- 9 (4.285)	Yes-15(7.14) No-13(6.19)	Yes-13(6.19) No-15 (7.142)	Yes-8(3.80) No-20(9.52)	Yes-10(4.76) No-18(8.57)
46-55	Yes-6 (2.857) No-13 (6.190)	Yes-10 (4.761) No-9 (4.285)	Yes-12 (5.71) No-7 (6.666)	Yes-11 (5.238) No-8 (3.809)	Yes-6 (2.857) No-13 (6.190)	C. Yes-5 (2.380) No-10(4.761) D. Yes- 4 (1.904)	Yes-8(3.80) No-11(5.238)	Yes-6(2.85) No-13(6.19)	Yes-6(2.85) No-13(6.19)	Yes-9(4.28) No-10(4.76)
56-60	Yes-7 (3.333) No-8 (3.809)	Yes-8 (3.809) No-7 (3.333)	Yes-12 (5.714) No-3 (1.428)	Yes-7 (3.333) No-8 (3.809)	Yes-6 (2.857) No-9 (4.285)	C. Yes-3 (1.428) No-6(2.857) D. Yes- 6 (2.857)	Yes-8(3.80) No-7(3.33)	Yes-5(2.38) No-10(4.76)	Yes-6(2.85) No-9(4.28)	Yes-8(3.80) No-7(3.33)

- Table: 4 shows the symptoms of migraine.
- In the age group of 15-20, obesity was 4.285%, sensitive to light in 10.95%, to sound in 10%, to smell in 9.047%, fatigue in 10%, constipation and diarrhea in 3.809% and 4.285%, not being able to see in 7.6%, tingling or numbness in 7.16%, not being able to speak in 6.19%, changes in smell taste or touch in 6.66%.
- In the age group of 21-30, obesity was 10.476%, sensitive to light in 17.14%, to sound in 19.04%, to smell in 13.33%, fatigue in 11.4%, constipation and diarrhea in 8.571% and 14.76%, not being able to see in 13.3%, tingling or numbness in 20%, not being able to speak in 13.33%, changes in smell taste or touch in 13.33%
- In the age group of 31-35, obesity was 9.523%, sensitive to light in 8.571%, to sound in 5.619%, to smell in 8.09%, fatigue-9.047%, constipation and diarrhea in 6.66% and 2.380%, not being able to see in 10%, tingling or numbness in 10%, not being able to speak in 4.28%, changes in smell taste or touch in 5.23%.
- In the age group of 36-40, obesity was 4.761%, sensitive to light in 7.142%, to sound in 6.666%, to smell in 7.619%, fatigue 3.809%, constipation and diarrhea in 2.857% and 2.857%, not being able to see in 8.09%, tingling or numbness in 8.57%, not

being able to speak in 3.80%, changes in smell taste or touch in 4.28%.

- In the age group of 41-45, obesity was 4.761%, sensitive to light in 7.142%, to sound in 6.666%, to smell in 7.619%, fatigue 6.190%, constipation and diarrhea in 4.285% and 4.285%, not being able to see in 7.14%, tingling or numbness in 6.19%, not being able to speak in 3.80%, changes in smell taste or touch in 4.76%
- In the age group of 46-55 obesity was 2.857%, sensitive to light in 4.761%, to sound in 5.71%, to smell in 5.238%, fatigue in 2.857%, constipation and diarrhea in 2.380% and 1.904%, not being able to see in 3.80%, tingling or numbness in 2.85%, not being able to speak in 2.85%, changes in smell taste or touch in 4.28%.
- In the age group of 56-60 obesity was 3.333%, sensitive to light in 3.809%, to sound in 5.714%, to smell in 3.333%, fatigue in 2.857%, constipation and diarrhea in 1.428% and 2.857%, not being able to see in 3.80%, tingling or numbness in 2.38%, not being able to speak in 2.85%, changes in smell taste or touch in 3.80%

Table 5: Causes of Migraine by Age Group.

Age Group	Stress	Physical activity	Medications	Foods	Skipping meals	Caffeine	Changes in weather	Senses. noises, lights,	(Loud bright and	Tobacco	Hypersomnia
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								strong smells)		
15-20	Yes-27 (12.85) No-10 (4.761)	Yes-22 (10.47) No-15 (7.142)	Yes-14 (6.66) No-23 (10.952)	Yes-17 (8.095) No-20 (9.523)	Yes-19 (9.047) No-18 (8.571)	Yes-9 (4.285) No-28 (13.33)	Yes-17 (8.095) No-20 (9.523)	Yes-24 (11.428) No-13 (6.190)	All No	Yes-12 (5.714) No-25 (11.904)
21-30	Yes-47 (22.38) No-15 (7.142)	Yes-31 (14.76) No-31 (14.76)	Yes-26 (12.380) No-36 (17.142)	Yes-28 (13.33) No-34 (16.19)	Yes-32 (15.238) No-30 (14.285)	Yes-21 (10) No-41 (19.523)	Yes-36 (17.14) No-26 (12.380)	Yes-34 (16.190) No-28 (13.33)	Yes-11 (5.238) No-51 (24.28)	Yes-27 (12.85) No-35 (16.66)
31-35	Yes-19 (9.04) No-6 (2.857)	Yes-11 (5.238) No-14 (6.66)	Yes-21 (10) No-4 (1.904)	Yes-13 (6.190) No-12 (5.714)	Yes-12 (5.714) No-13 (7.619)	Yes-13 (6.196) No-12 (5.714)	Yes-15 (7.142) No-10 (4.761)	Yes-23 (10.95) No-2 (0.952)	Yes-3 (1.428) No-22 (10.47)	Yes-9 (4.285) No-16 (7.619)
36-40	Yes-20 (9.523) No-4 (1.904)	Yes-19 (9.047) No-5 (2.380)	Yes-12 (5.714) No-12 (5.714)	Yes-18 (8.571) No-16 (7.619)	Yes-15 (7.142) No-9 (4.285)	Yes-18 (8.571) No-6 (2.857)	Yes-14 (6.66) No-10 (4.761)	Yes-19 (9.047) No-5 (2.380)	Yes-3 (1.428) No-21 (10)	Yes-11 (5.238) No-13 (6.190)
41-45	Yes-14 (6.666) No-14 (6.666)	Yes-15 (7.142) No-13 (6.190)	Yes-17 (8.095) No-11 (5.238)	Yes-17 (8.095) No-11 (5.238)	Yes-12 (5.714) No-16 (7.619)	Yes-9 (4.285) No-19 (9.047)	Yes-15 (7.142) No-13 (6.190)	Yes-19 (9.047) No-9 (4.285)	Yes-4 (1.904) No-24 (11.42)	Yes-11 (5.238) No-17 (8.095)
46-55	Yes-13 (6.190) No-6 (2.857)	Yes-8 (3.809) No-11 (5.238)	Yes-11 (5.238) No-8 (3.809)	Yes-13 (6.190) No-6 (2.857)	Yes-7 (3.33) No-12 (5.714)	Yes-8 (3.809) No-11 (5.238)	Yes-12 (5.714) No-7 (3.33)	Yes-9 (4.285) No-5 (4.761)	Yes-5 (2.380) No-14 (6.666)	Yes-7 (3.33) No-12 (5.714)
56-60	Yes-9 (4.285) No-6 (2.857)	Yes-12 (5.714) No-3 (1.428)	Yes-11 (5.238) No-4 (1.904)	Yes-9 (4.285) No-6 (2.857)	Yes-3 (1.428) No-12 (5.714)	Yes-8 (3.809) No-7 (3.33)	Yes-4 (1.904) No-11 (5.238)	Yes-12 (5.714) No-3 (1.428)	Yes- (2.380) No-10 (4.761)	Yes-7 (3.33) No-8 (0.952)

- Table: 5 shows the causes of migraine
- In the age group of 15-20, causes include: stress in 12.85%, physically active in 10.47%, using medicines in 6.66%, intake of food in 8.095%, skipping meals in 9.047%, intake of caffeine in 4.285%, noticing changes in weather in 8.095%, reacting to senses in 11.428%, using tobacco in 0%, and with hypersomnia in 5.714%.
- In the age group of 21-30, causes include: stress in 22.38%, physically active in 14.76%, using medicines in 12.380%, intake of food in 13.33%, skipping meals in 15.238%, intake of caffeine in 10%, noticing changes in weather in 17.14%, reacting to senses in 16.190%, using tobacco in 5.238%, and with hypersomnia in 12.85%.
- In the age group of 31-35, causes include: stress in 9.04%, physically active in 5.238%, using medicines in 10%, intake of food in 6.190%, skipping meals in 5.714%, intake of caffeine in 6.196%, noticing changes in weather in 7.142%, reacting to senses in 10.95%, using tobacco in 1.428%, and with hypersomnia in 4.285%.
- In the age group of 36-40, causes include: stress in 9.523%, physically active in 9.047%, using medicines in 5.714%, intake of food in 8.571%, skipping meals in 7.142%, intake of caffeine in 8.571%, noticing changes in weather in 6.666%, reacting to senses in 9.047%, using tobacco in 1.428%, and with hypersomnia in 5.238%.
- In the age group of 41-45, causes include: stress in 6.666%, physically active in 7.142%, using medicines in 8.095%, intake of food in 8.095%, skipping meals in 5.714%, intake of caffeine in 4.285%, noticing changes in weather in 7.142%, reacting to senses in 9.047%, using tobacco in 1.904%, and with hypersomnia in 5.238%.
- In the age group of 46-55, causes include: stress in 6.190%, physically active in 3.809%, using medicines in 5.238%, intake of food in 6.190%, skipping meals in 3.33%, intake of caffeine in 3.809%, noticing changes in weather in 5.714%, reacting to senses in 4.285%, using tobacco in 2.380%, and with hypersomnia in 3.33%.
- In the age group of 56-60, causes include: stress in 4.285%, physically active in 5.714%, using medicines in 5.238%, intake of food in 4.285%, skipping meals in 1.428%, intake of caffeine in 3.809%, noticing changes in weather in 1.904%, reacting to senses in 5.71%, using tobacco in 2.380%, and with hypersomnia in 3.333%.

Table 6: Types of Migraine by Age.

Age Group	Migraine with aura	Migraine without aura,	Menstrual migraine
15-20	16 (7.619)	13 (6.190)	8 (3.809)

21-30	21 (10)	31 (14.761)	10 (4.761)
31-35	9 (4.285)	13 (6.190)	3 (1.428)
36-40	10 (4.761)	9 (4.285)	5 (2.380)
41-45	12 (5.714)	9 (4.285)	7 (3.333)
46-55	11 (5.238)	8 (3.809)	-
56-60	12 (5.714)	3 (1.428)	-

- Table 6: shows the types of migraines by age.
- In the age group of 15-20, migraine with aura was 7.619%, migraine without aura was 6.190%, and menstrual migraine was 3.809%.
- In the age group of 21-30, migraine with aura was 10%, migraine without aura was 14.761%, and menstrual migraine was 4.761%.
- In the age group of 31-35, migraine with aura was 4.285%, migraine without aura was 6.190%, and menstrual migraine was 1.428%.
- In the age group of 36-40, migraine with aura was 4.761%, migraine without aura was 4.285%, and menstrual migraine was 2.380%.
- In the age group of 41-45, migraine with aura was 5.714%, migraine without aura was 4.285%, and menstrual migraine was 3.333%.
- In the age group of 46-55, migraine with aura was 5.238%, migraine without aura was 3.809%, and no cases of menstrual migraine.
- In the age group of 56-60, migraine with aura was 5.714%, migraine without aura was 1.428%, and no cases of menstrual migraine.

DISCUSSION

Migraine is a common neurological disease that causes a variety of symptoms, most notably a throbbing, pulsing headache on one side of the head. The exact cause of migraines is unknown. They are thought to be the result of abnormal brain activity temporarily affecting nerve signals, chemicals and blood vessels in the brain. Around half of all people who experience migraines, have a close relative with the condition. This suggests that genes may play a role. In the present study, the females of age group 15-20 were found to be more vulnerable.^[3] to migraine and also followed by 21-30 age groups in females, as they are all students and more stressful due to their irregular lifestyle and other general health conditions.^[2] Males are less prone to this problem. Severe migraine was observed in 31-35 age group in both the sexes. Mild migraine was detected in 15-20 age groups as they have earlier stage of head ache. In 21-30 age groups, all different kinds of general health problems were associated with migraine, and suffered from severe symptoms. This is because of irregular food habits, insomnia, consuming fast foods and caffeine, electronic

media. The migraine-related disability is high among the students.

Suggestions and Conclusion

- Find a calm environment
- Turn off the lights.
- Try temperature therapy.
- Sip a caffeinated drink.
- Sleep well
- Establish regular sleep hours.
- Unwind at the end of the day.
- Lessen distractions.
- Don't try so hard to sleep.
- Check your medicine.
- Eat wisely
- Avoid foods that trigger migraines.
- Exercise regularly.
- Manage stress
- Simplify your life.
- Manage your time wisely.
- Take a break.
- Adjust your attitude.
- Enjoy yourself.
- Relax.
- Strive for balance

Living with migraines is a daily challenge. But making healthy lifestyle choices can help. Ask your friends and loved ones for support. There is no one approach to treating migraines. Each case must be individualized according to its comorbidities.^[4]

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